

Inorganic Chemistry – Its Journey through Time[†]

D. Banerjea*

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Historically Inorganic Chemistry is the oldest branch of chemistry and its origin can be traced to the knowledge acquired, presumably through accidental discoveries, by people in the very ancient civilizations as in Egypt, India and Mesopotamia (in India *ca.* 2500 B.C.)¹. In subsequent period the Alchemists in China, in Egypt, in India (*ca.* 700-1100 A.D.) and later in Europe (*ca.* 1200-1500 A.D.) despite their queer views and objectives made discoveries that contributed to the advancement of this branch of chemistry¹. Extraction of zinc from the mineral calamine was first achieved in India by the alchemist Nagarjuna (9th century A.D.). Birth of modern inorganic chemistry is rightly attributed to the French chemist A. L. Lavoisier's systematic studies on the phenomenon of combustion that established (1772 A.D.) the role of oxygen in a combustion process leading to demolition of the classical *phlogiston theory* of Becher, and of Stahl (17th century A.D.).

Discovery of elements (Table 1) is an useful parameter of progress in inorganic chemistry. Some 30 ele-

Table-1 (contd.)

1903-1940 A.D.	<i>Tc, Pm, Eu, Lu, Hf, Re, At, Fr, Pa, Rn, Np, Pu</i>
1944-1969 A.D.	<i>Am, Cm, Bk, Cf, Es, Fr, Mv, No, Lr, Ku, Ha</i>
By 1989 A.D.	Elements of atomic number (Z) = 106-109 made artificially
By 1996	Z = 110-112
By 2010 A.D.	Z = 113-118

*Didymium (Di) was reported by Carl Mosander in the year 1843; this was later (1885) shown to be a mixture of the two elements Praseodymium (Pr) and Neodymium (Nd), which form light green and light pink coloured salts respectively and hence the mixture was colourless; the separation was effected by C. F. Auer von Welsbach in the year 1885.

**Terbium (Tb) was discovered by Carl Mosander in the year 1842 and from this another element Dysprosium (Dy) was isolated and characterized by Lecoq de Boisbaudran.

***Ytterbium (Yb) was discovered by J. D. G. Marignac in the year 1878, and from its salts Georges Urbain separated another element Lutetium (Lu) by fractional crystallization repeated 15,000 times.

The symbols in italic represent elements prepared by nuclear reactions.

Table 1. Discovery of elements

Period/Age	Elements discovered/known
Prehistoric	C, S, Au
<i>ca.</i> 3000 B.C.	Ag, Cu, Pb, Sn, Hg
<i>ca.</i> 1200 B.C.	Fe
<i>ca.</i> 500 B.C.	Zn (known as its alloy with copper, brass)
1750-1800 A.D.	H, N, O, F, P, As, Te, Sb, Be, Ti, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Bi, Zr, Mo, W, Pt, U
1801-1863 A.D.	B, Si, Cl, Br, I, Se, Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs, Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, Cd, Al, In, Tl, Y, La, Ce, V, Nb, Ta, Th, Pd, Ru, Rh, Os, Ir, Er, (Di)*, (Tb)**
1868-1899 A.D.	He, Ne, Ar, Kr, Xe, Sc, Ga, Ge, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Dy, Ho, Tm, Po, Ra, Ac, (Yb)***

ments were discovered by 1800 A.D. and another 54 by 1900 A.D., while the rest (including many prepared artificially by nuclear reactions) mostly in the 20th century and so far the highest element made and characterized is of atomic number 118 (*un-un-octium*). A plot of the discovery of elements vs time mirrors the pattern of developments in many other fields of science including chemistry.

Some of the significant developments in inorganic chemistry and in other areas that impacted the progress in inorganic chemistry in the 19th century are summarised in Table 2.

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

*Former Sir Rashbehary Ghose Professor of Chemistry (Retired), Calcutta University, E-mail : banerjeas2005@yahoo.co.in

Table 2. Some Landmark Developments in Chemistry (19th century)

Year	Item
1803	Atomic theory (Dalton)
1811	Avogadro's hypothesis, recognition of molecules
1827	[PtCl ₂ (C ₂ H ₄) ₂] (Zeise)
1829	Dulong and Patit's law
1831	K[PtCl ₃ (C ₂ H ₄)]·H ₂ O (Zeise's salt)
1832-33	Laws of electrolysis (Faraday)
1848	Zn(CH ₃) ₂ (Frankland)
1852	Joule-Thomson (Lord Kelvin) effect
1858-76	Cathode rays (Goldstein, 1876)
1860-65	Determination of atomic weights (Stass) (Richards, 1904)
1867	Law of mass action (Guldberg and Waag)*
1869	Periodic law (Mendeleev) and Periodic Tables (Mendeleev, Lothar Meyer)
1873	Molecular weight from vapour density (Viator Meyer)
1885	Separation of Di into Pr and Nd (Welsbach, see foot-note in Table 1)
1886	Ge (Winkler), F ₂ (Moissan), Al (Hall-Herault process)
1887	N ₂ H ₄ (Curtis)
1888	Theory of electrolytic dissociation (Arrhenius)
1888	Ni(CO) ₄ (Mond)
1889	Dilution law (Ostwald), Le Chatlier's principle
1889	Concept of activation energy of a reaction (Arrhenius)
1890	[Pt(NH ₃) ₄][Pt(NH ₃)Cl ₃] ₂
1890	Molecular weight by limiting density (Bertholet)
1893	Coordination theory (Werner)
1894	He (in minerals) (Ramsay)
1894	Ne, Ar, Kr, Xe from air (Raleigh)
1895	X-Rays (Röntgen)
1896	Radioactivity (Becquerel)
1897	e/m of cathode ray particles (Thomson)
1898	Ra and Po from pitchblende (Pierre and Marie Curie)
1899	Ac (Debiere)
1900	RMgX (Grignard)

*Although the basic postulate about the rate of a chemical reaction is not valid always, the equilibrium expression that it leads to, known as the Law of Chemical Equilibrium, is valid always.

The significant advances that took place in the 20th century, particularly since the 1950s, were due to advent of a number of sophisticated physico-chemical techniques that provided precise and detailed information on structures and bond features of molecular species. The developments in nuclear science provided further impetus to vigorous activity in inorganic chemistry. During the last century there has been developments that considerably widened the domain of inorganic chemistry. A concise

account of such developments has been presented by the author in an article published in an issue of this Journal^{2(a)} in the year 2000 and another review on the mechanistic aspects of reactions of metal complexes, a thriving area of research in inorganic chemistry, has also been published by the author^{2(b)} in this Journal in the year 2003. In this connection the Proceedings of the 4th Dalton Discussions held in the year 2002 is worth noting^{3(a)}. The 20th century was indeed a golden age for inorganic chemistry, one of intense activity and curiosity-driven research^{3(b)} and the trend is continuing. Since the 1950s we also notice the emergence of bioinorganic chemistry and considerable activity in elucidating the role of metal ions in biological systems⁴. In the present article some of the salient developments reported mostly during the first decade of the present century will be presented briefly; the coverage is illustrative but is surely not comprehensive.

The Dalton division of the Royal Society of Chemistry, UK, has held jointly with the European Chemical Society an international conference on inorganic chemistry at Manchester (UK) during April 11-14 this year (2011). The invited lectures delivered and sessions held on the following areas specifically, are indeed some of the major areas of current activity in inorganic chemistry : (a) Supramolecular chemistry, (b) Organometallic chemistry and Catalysis, (c) Reaction mechanisms, (d) Inorganic materials, (e) Energy and Photochemistry, (f) Bioinorganic chemistry and Metalloenzymes, (g) Chemistry of Main Group Elements and (h) Solid state chemistry.

At the juncture of the 20th and 21st century it was realised that there is an urgent need for an alternative and sustainable source of clean energy because of fast depletion of the natural fossil fuels^{5,6} and the environmental pollution caused by their use. The total energy that reaches the earth from the sun in one hour is adequate to meet our present energy demand in the world. But the technology is yet to be developed for efficient and economical harnessing of solar energy. Nuclear energy is another option, but there are various problems associated with the production of nuclear energy, particularly the disposal of the highly radioactive spent fuel of nuclear power plants, apart from radiation hazard in case of an accident in a nuclear power plant and a few such cases are already known such as the one at the Chernobyl plant in the

erstwhile Soviet union during the eighties (1986) of the last century, another in the Three Mile Island in the USA and a recent one caused by a natural calamity at Fukushima (Japan) in the month of March this year (2011). On various considerations hydrogen seems to have the potential to be the ideal fuel of the future, provided we can develop the technology for its large scale production from our vast reserve of water using the solar energy for splitting water forming H_2 and O_2 and overcome the problem of storage and transportation of hydrogen which is indeed challenging. Burning the hydrogen produces water releasing considerable amount of usable energy and the water from which the hydrogen is generated is reproduced on burning the hydrogen making hydrogen a sustainable unending source of green energy. While gaseous or liquid hydrogen is currently an option for prototype motor vehicles, solid state storage of hydrogen is superior both in terms of storage capacity and safety⁶. Hence storage of large quantity of hydrogen in a compact solid medium from which the hydrogen can be released easily and conveniently as and when needed is one of the challenges to be met for large scale use of hydrogen as a fuel and there is considerable ongoing activity in this area⁶ and the major developments during the period up to 2008 have been reviewed^{7(a)}. Several papers on *s*-block metals and their compounds either as components of MOF or amidoborane derivatives as hydrogen storage media appeared in the year 2009^{7(b)-(h)}.

Both the uptake and release of hydrogen must be thermodynamically and kinetically favourable to be useful. The storage may be both chemical (as a compound) or physical (surface adsorption or interstitial absorption in a porous framework material) involving Van der Waals type interaction. Among the chemical storage materials studied so far are metals/metal alloys and their hydrides and complex hydrides⁸⁻²¹ and various other hydrogen containing compounds²²⁻⁶¹.

Chemical Storage of Hydrogen

Among chemical storage materials we have several metal alloys; both Mg_2Ni (storage capacity 3.6% w/w Hydrogen) and $LaNi_5$ (1.28% w/w) are two of the well-studied examples. They have extraordinary cycleability^{8(c)}. $Fe_{0.15}Ti_{0.85}V$ alloy has a storage capacity of 3.7%^{8(d)}, while $V_3Ti_{3.5}Cr_{2.5}Fe$ has a maximum capacity of 3.6%

(2% efficiently even at 25°C)^{8(e)} and two recently reported are $TiCrV$ and $TiCrVMo$ ^{8(f)} alloys (see p. 1129). Light metal hydrides like MgH_2 (7.6% w/w) are important due to high storage capacity but have the disadvantage because of high temperature needed for desorption of hydrogen, as also unfavourable thermodynamics and kinetics⁹. Despite such limitations MgH_2 is one of the binary hydrides that is receiving much attention because of its light weight and high storage capacity¹⁰. Electrochemical synthesis of AlH_3 from $MAiH_4$ ($M = Li, Na, K$) has been reported, opening up its potential use as a hydrogen storage material¹¹. But complex hydrides like $LiBH_4$, $LiAlH_4$, as also imides and amides like Li_2NH and $LiNH_2$ are of greater promise because of their superiority over the binary hydrides in several respects^{9,12-15}. Considerable amount of work is being done on MgH_2 to improve its performance¹⁶⁻¹⁹. The lightest of complex hydrides, $LiBH_4$, has received much attention due to its high storage capacity (18.4% w/w)^{12,20}. But its high decomposition temperature ($\geq 380^\circ C$) and unfavourable kinetic and thermodynamic reversibility are challenges that are yet to be overcome for its use as a suitable hydrogen storage material. $Mg(AlH_4)_2$ (9.3% w/w) has a lower decomposition temperature (140–200°C) and even better in this regard is $LiAlH_4$ (cap., 9.3% w/w, dec. 125°C); still better is $Al(BH_4)_3$ (cap., 16.8% w/w, dec. 20°C) and these are of much promise. Reversible absorption and desorption from alanates (aluminumhydrides) has been shown to be catalysed by Ti and this has created much interest and research activity in the field. But no other metal dopant shows any activity comparable to that of Ti. $LiBH_4$ doped with TiF_3 releases 5.7% hydrogen at 70–90°C as against 380°C for the undoped material (*loc. cit.*)²¹. Dehydrogenation of $Mg(BH_4)_2$ starts at ca. 227°C but this drops to 88°C if doped with $TiCl_3$.

Chan *et al.*²² reported reversible uptake of hydrogen by Li_3N leading to considerable activity on Li–N–H and Li–E–N–H ($E = \text{Group I and Group II metal}$) systems²³⁻³⁸. While hydrogen desorption from $LiNH_2$ occurs at $\geq 250^\circ C$, for $(Li_{1-x}Mg_{0.5x})NH_2$ the desorption occurs at 100°C²⁷. Doping with Ca or Mg considerably reduces the hydrogen desorption temperature of hydrogenated Li_2NH ³⁶. Reversible storage in a LiH – $LiNH_2$

has been reported^{22,23} and this releases hydrogen under favourable conditions. Several other binary hydride + amide combinations such as LiH–Mg(NH₂)₂ have been investigated^{39–54}. Addition of KH to Mg(NH₂)₂–LiH greatly improves performance; the desorption begins at 80°C and ca. 5% hydrogen can be reversibly desorbed/absorbed at ca. 107°C^{7(e)}. Analogously, a 2 : 1 mixture of LiBH₄ and MgH₂ has a lower decomposition temperature⁴⁴ than LiBH₄. Both hydrogenation and dehydrogenation kinetics are improved by the MgH₂ :

A reversible storage capacity of over 9% (w/w) (theor., 11.9%) has been demonstrated for the system (eq. 1) when catalysed by doping with 2.3 mole % of TiCl₃.

Another system^{47,48} investigated is,

Another is LiAlH₄ + LiNH₂ system (overall, eq. 3)⁵¹, while another is a Li–Al–N–H system^{52,53(a)} doped with TiCl₃ + (1/3) AlCl₃; the system is 100% reversible and releases 7.1% hydrogen in two steps (overall, eq. 4) :

For NaAlH₄, reducing particle size from 1–10 μm to 2–10 nm reduces the desorption temperature from 186°C to 70°C with enhancement of rate^{53(b)}.

A mixture (1 : 1 mole ratio) of LiAlH₄ + Mg(NH₂)₂ having a hydrogen content of 8.5% releases 6.2% hydrogen under ball-milling near ambient temperature⁵⁴ :

Similar studies on ternary systems such as LiNH₂ + LiBH₄ + MgH₂ (2 : 1 : 1 mole ratio) have been reported^{55–57} and some of these appear to be of promise.

Ammonia-borane, H₃N.BH₃, is an attractive compound; its capacity is 19.6% (the hydrogen content exceeds that of gasoline)^{58–61}. Its stepwise decomposition in the solid state releases 12% hydrogen :

Several approaches including catalysis by *d*-block metals have been made to speed up the release of hydrogen^{59,62–70} and reduce the temperature of dehydrogenation⁵⁹. Alkali metal amidoboranes, such as LiNH₂.BH₃ and NaNH₂.BH₃ release 10.9% and 7.5% hydrogen respectively at ca. 90°C :

Ca(H₂N.BH₃)₂ releases hydrogen smoothly over a temperature range of 100–170°C⁷¹. Despite several advantages of such systems, the most serious drawback is lack of facile reversibility which makes these compounds unsuitable for hydrogen storage applications.

Physical Storage

Chabazite (a natural zeolite) can trap within its channels up to 1.3% hydrogen^{72(a)} compared to 0.67% by Pd.

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are a type of coordination polymers having ordered network of cavities and pores in their structural framework (three-dimensional) as in the zeolites. Hence, various small molecules including those of liquids and gases can diffuse in and out of the channels, often selectively and many such materials have exceptionally high hydrogen storage capacity. Their primary building blocks are multidentate polymeric organic ligands with their donors linked (coordinated) to metal or cluster of metal atoms. These MOFs are useful H₂ storage materials (first reported in the year 2003)^{72(b)}. Thus, a Zn-containing framework (MOF-5) of composition Zn₄O(BDC) (BDC = 1,4-benzene-dicarboxylate) takes up^{72(b)} 4.5% hydrogen at –195°C and only 1% at ambient temperature and pressure of 20 bar of H₂. A topologically similar MOF-8 having naphthalene linkers replacing BDC takes up to 2% hydrogen at room temperature and a pressure of 10 bar H₂^{72(b)}. Another independent observation⁷³ on MOF-5 reported 4.5–5.2% uptake of hydrogen at –196°C and pressure of ca. 50 bar. Several strategies to improve hydrogen storage capacity of MOFs under more favourable working conditions have also been reported⁷⁴. These include adjustment of pore size in the MOF to match the diameter of the H₂ molecule to increase Van der Waals interaction with H₂ and use of coordinatively unsaturated metal centres or open metal sites that enables M–H₂ interaction. A variety of framework materials have been synthesized and investigated for the purpose of hydrogen storage applications^{73–86}. MOFs with unsaturated coordination po-

sitions or open metal sites have been shown to be rather attractive for hydrogen storage^{75,76,82,87-90}. Use of “H₂ spill over” technique causes 8-fold increase in H₂ uptake in MOF⁹¹.

More recently many of the so-called covalent organic frameworks (COFs) have been synthesized having the structural units linked by C–C, C–O, B–O, Si–C, etc., bonds in place of metal atoms, and these have been shown to be excellent for hydrogen storage⁹²⁻⁹⁵. In COF-8 the uptake of hydrogen is 10% at –196°C and pressure of 100 bar^{95(a)}. Best result obtained so far is with a Cu-based MOF^{95(b)} that takes up to 10% hydrogen at 77 bar and –196°C.

Newer Hydrogen Storage Materials

Nanowires of Mg have been shown⁹⁶ to have enhanced rate of hydrogen absorption/desorption compared to bulk MgH₂ (which despite its high capacity suffers from the disadvantage of an unfavourable rate). Although after 10 cycles of adsorption/desorption there is complete collapse of the nanowires to nanoparticles no change in hydrogen absorption capacity has been noticed even after 50 cycles⁹⁶. Magnesium nanoparticles of 5 nm diameter have reversible hydrogen storage capacity of 7.6% at room temperature⁹⁷. The efficacy of NaAlH₄ also depends on size⁹⁸. With NaAlH₄ nanoparticles of size 2–10 nm hydrogen desorption occurs below 70°C, which can be followed by reabsorption at low hydrogen pressures beginning at 20 bar⁹⁸.

Nanoparticles of Mg(NH₂)₂ mixed with 2 moles of MgH₂ nanoparticles desorb hydrogen at 102°C with enhanced rate compared to the bulk materials⁹⁹. Prospects of metal/metal hydride nanoparticles for storage of hydrogen has been reviewed mentioning their advantages and disadvantages¹⁰⁰. Carbon nanotubes¹⁰¹, porous carbon¹⁰², clathrates¹⁰³⁻¹⁰⁶ and zeolites^{3(b),107} have been investigated as high storage capacity materials for storage of hydrogen. The stored hydrogen can be released either by changing the temperature or the pressure. Nanowires and nanotubes of BN, TiS₂, MoS₂, etc. are also under investigation as prospective hydrogen storage materials^{108(a)}. Nanotubes of synthetic Cu and Mg silicates have better thermal stability than zeolites and have good hydrogen storage capacity^{108(b)}.

Photocatalysts for Water Splitting

Ever since the discovery over 30 years ago of ruthenium complexes of bipyridine as photocatalysts for the photochemical splitting of water using sunlight, there has

been significant research activity in search for more efficient such photocatalysts and polypyridyl complexes of ruthenium continue to be an active area of research for their application as sensitizing chromophores in dye-sensitized solar cell applications, and quite a few such systems have been reported during the last decade^{109,110}. Gratzel and coworkers have reported several Ru(II) complexes of the type Ru(L–L)(L′–L′)(NCS)₂ where L–L and L′–L′ are 4,4′-disubstituted-2,2′-bipyridines, as sensitizers for photovoltaic solar cells to generate electricity using solar energy^{110(a)-(d)}. Such an efficient ruthenium complex reported by them^{110(e)} is *cis*-[Ru(4,4′-bis-(5-octylthieno[3,2-*b*]thiophene-2-yl)-2,2′-bipyridine)(4,4′-dicarboxylic acid-2,2′-bipyridine)(NCS)₂] which has a high molar extinction coefficient (ϵ_m , $2.05 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 553 nm) that gives power conversion efficiency of 10.53% under irradiation of air mass 1.5 global (AM 1.5 G) full sunlight^{110(e)}. This group also reported another such complex [Ru(4,4′-bis(5-hexylfuran-2-yl)-2,2′-bipyridine)(4,4′-dicarboxylic acid-2,2′-bipyridine)(NCS)₂] that gives conversion efficiency of 11.0–11.3%^{110(f)}. An improvement is the use of a Ru complex devoid of SCN[–] which is likely to be of longer active life^{110(g)} and a cobalt and phosphorous based cheaper O₂ evolving catalyst on In₂O₃ + SnO₂ electrode¹¹¹. The complex [Ru(L–L)(dcb)(NCS)₂] (dcb = 4,4′-dicarboxylate-2,2′-bipyridine, L–L = 4,4′-R₂-2,2′-bipyridine, where R =) as sensitizer gives excellent power conversion of 11.5%^{112(a)}. Another similar complex (ϵ_m , $2.74 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 521 nm) yields 10.7% conversion^{112(b)}.

Another such complex (ϵ_m , $1.93 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 547 nm) gives 8% conversion^{112(c)}. TiO₂ photoanode for dye-sensitized solar cells has been reported^{112(d)}. Photochemical generation of H₂ from water using sunlight and recombinant human serum albumin (rHSA) complex with Zn-protoporphyrin-IX (ZnPP) has been reported¹¹³. The hydrogen generating system was made of a phosphate buffered aqueous solution (pH, 5.4) containing colloidal poly(vinylalcohol)-Pt as catalyst, the above stated Zn complex as the sensitizer and methyl viologen (MV²⁺) as electron acceptor with triethanolamine as sacrificial electron donor. This on irradiation from a 450 watt xenon arc lamp with a heat absorption filter (330–700 nm) that cuts off UV radiation led to steady evolution of hydrogen during the entire period of observation (6 h) at 25°C. On

irradiation rHSA-ZnPP forms rHSA-^{3r}ZnPP* (triplate excited state) which reacts with MV²⁺ forming (rHSA-ZnPP⁺)* and (MV⁺)*. Electron transfer from (rHSA-^{3r}ZnPP)* to MV²⁺ followed by the reduction of (rHSA-ZnPP⁺)* by triethanolamine (which gets oxidized to an oxidized form) is the crucial step in the process. The excited state species (MV⁺)* drives the reduction of H₂O to H₂ in presence of the colloidal poly(vinylalcohol)-Pt catalyst; the MV²⁺ acts as an electron relay. Metalloporphyrins as potential sensitizers for efficient dye-sensitized solar cells has been reviewed^{114(a)}. Hydrogenase function and its role in hydrogen production has been reviewed^{114(b)}.

Armstrong and coworkers (UK)^{115(a)} have reported their success in making a hydrogen producing system by attaching a Se-Ni-Fe hydrogenase enzyme and a light-harvesting Ru(II) dye to TiO₂ particles which in contact with water releases H₂ on being irradiated with sunlight. They are also planning to incorporate a water oxidation catalyst into the device that would cause water-splitting generating O₂ + 2H₂ that can be fed into a fuel cell for generation of electricity. Incorporation of the Se into the hydrogenase made it tolerant to inhibition by H₂ and O₂ and also gave a stronger binding of the hydrogenase to the TiO₂ which serves as electron carrier. The system can be suspended in water or a buffer solution and irradiated with sunlight giving a steady evolution of H₂. The Ru(II) dye is the complex Ru(bipy)₂(L-L) where L-L is a 2,2'-bipyridine with HPO₃ substituent in the 4 position of each pyridine ring. A black TiO₂ made by hydrogenation of TiO₂ absorbs light over a wide range (UV-VIS-IR) and hence better than the doped TiO₂ used so far (which absorbs only in the UV) in solar cells for water splitting and electricity generation^{115(b)}. Hydrogen production from biomass and fossil fuels has been reviewed¹¹⁶.

Developments in the Chemistry of Elements

A remarkable development in hydrogen chemistry is the demonstration of H of mass number 7 as an extremely transient species that is formed on bombarding a ¹²C target with a beam of ⁸He¹¹⁷ :

Earlier studies reported (see Ref. 117) extremely transient ⁶H, ⁵H and ⁴H.

A group of Japanese workers (T. Hibino and coworkers of Nagoya University) have reported¹¹⁸ conversion of methane to methanol at 80°C (1 atm) in a H₂-O₂ fuel cell, i.e., under far less drastic conditions than in the commercial processes involving catalytic reaction between

CO and H₂. Using a feed of H₂ + CH₄ the CH₃OH is formed in the following overall process :

The *crown ethers* are a class of macrocyclic ligands known since 1967 (Pederson *et al.*) and cryptands are macropolycyclic ligands known since 1988 (Lehn). Hetero-macrocyclic systems having different macrocyclic units were reported in 2002¹¹⁹. The crown-ethers had been used earlier to make exotic salts like the *alkalides* and *electrides*^{2(a)}, and some other exotic salts having the *Zintl anions* and analogues such as the following :

[Rb(18-crown-6)]₄(As₁₄).6NH₃^{120(a)}, [K(18-crown-6)]₂(P₄).8.5NH₃^{120(b)}, [K(crypt-2,2,2)]₂[Ni@Pb₁₀] and [K(crypt-2,2,2)]₂[M@Pb₁₂]¹²¹ (M = Ni, Pd, Pt) and [M@Ge₁₀]³⁻ in K(crypt)⁺ salt (M = Fe^{122(a)}, Co^{122(b)}) (@ denotes encapsulation). The cluster anions Ni₂Sn₁₇⁴⁻ which has two Ni encapsulated Sn₈ units linked at one Sn vertex^{123(a)}, another in the salt [K(crypt-2,2,2)]₅(Zn₉Bi₁₁)^{123(b)} and [MAu_n]⁻ (M = Si, Ge, Sn; n = 5-8)¹²⁴. The polyiodide ions I_x⁻ (x = 3, 5) have been stabilised¹²⁵ similarly in salts of the cation Cs(benzo-18-crown-6)₂⁺. Tetrasodium tetradecaphosphide has been made and the structures of Na₄(DMF)_{7.5}P₁₄ and Na₄(en)₆P₁₄ have been described^{126(a)} and K₂(THF)₉ having zigzag S₉²⁻ chain^{126(b)}. Another exotic compound is K₁₇(Sb₈)₂(NH₂).17.5NH₃ which has been made by reduction of Sb with K in liquid NH₃. This contains crown-shaped Sb₈⁸⁻ Zintl ion (analogous to S₈ ring)¹²⁷. Reduction of C₆₀ fullerene with Rb in a mixture of DMF + THF in presence of benzo-18-crown-6 has enabled isolation of salt of C₆₀³⁻ with [Rb(benzo-18-crown-6)]⁺¹²⁸. Reacting white phosphorus with Li in liquid ammonia the compound Li(NH₃)₄P₁₄.NH₃ has been made; this has the anion (PP₆-PP₆)⁴⁻¹²⁹. The first triple-decker *lithocene* sandwich anion [(η⁵-Cp)Li(η⁵-Cp)Li(η⁵-Cp)]⁻ has been made¹³⁰ by reacting V(Cp)₂ with Li(X) (where X a pyrimidine derivative). A survey on deltahedral Zintl ions has been published¹³¹.

High nuclearity W₃₆ isopolytungstate cluster [H₁₂W₃₆O₁₂₀]¹²⁻ forms (like 18-crown-ethers) complexes with alkali metal ions K⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺ also with NH₄⁺ and the alkaline-earth cations Sr²⁺ and Ba²⁺¹³². Also interesting to note are the 'Clam-like' encapsulated Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ complexes formed by an aromatic hexaphenolic cyclotricatechylene having a bowl-shaped cavity; a pair of these joined face-to-face by hydrogen bonding forms

the ‘clam shell’ with the M^+ of appropriate size encapsulated within the shell (I) as the ‘clam meat’¹³³.

On heating $MgBr_2$ in a current of HCl gas the species $MgCl$ sublimes and this has been recovered as $Cl-Mg-Mg-Cl$ by matrix isolation; both species characterised by vibrational spectroscopy and are authentic $Mg(I)$ compounds^{134(a)}. Generation and structures of molecular compounds of $Mg(I)$ with $Mg-Mg$ covalent bond have been highlighted^{134(b)}. Reduction of two Mg iodide complexes with K in toluene has provided the thermally stable $Mg(I)$ compounds $L-Mg-Mg-L$ ($L = [(Dipp)NC(N^iPr_2)(Dipp)]^-$ or $[(Dipp)NC(Me)_2CH]^-$; $Dipp = 2,6$ -diisopropylphenyl)¹³⁵. Another one of $Mg(I)$ with $Mg-Mg$ bond reported subsequently¹³⁶ is shown below (II). An interest-

ing dinuclear complex of calcium having $Ca-C$ sigma bond has been reported (III)^{137(a)}.

In connection with compounds with metal-metal bonds it is worth noting that a $Zn(I)$ compound analogous to the $Mg(I)$ compound (II) has been reported^{138(a)} as also $Cp_2Zr(ZnR)_2$ with $Zr-Zn$ bonds^{138(b)} and another with $Zn-Ga$ bonds^{138(c)}. Even more interesting is $(Cp^*)_2Ba-$

$\{Ga(Cp^*)\}_2$ having two $Ba-Ga$ bonds¹³⁹. Examples of such unsupported $Mg-Ga$ and $Ca-Ga$ ¹⁴⁰, also $U-Ga$, $U-Re$ and $Fe-Nd$ bonds¹⁴¹ are known, as also a (2-c, 2-e) $Be-Pt$ bond in the following examples^{142(a)} (a) and (b) :

Several other cases of compounds with $M-M$ bonds have been reported recently^{142(b)-(g)}. Metal cluster compounds are an important class in which there are significant $M-M$ bonding interactions and we have numerous recent examples^{142(h)-(n),361}.

Compounds with $M-M$ multiple bonds with bond order up to 4 were known earlier. But a Cr_2 compound with $Cr-Cr$ quintuple bond (bond order 5) was first reported in 2005^{143(a),(b)} followed by that in a Mo_2 compound in 2009^{143(c)}.

During the year 2006 several aspects of boron chemistry have been reviewed, viz., polymeric materials containing Lewis acidic boron sites and their applications as luminescent and optical materials, and chemical and electrochemical sensors^{144(a)}, photoelectron spectroscopic and theoretical studies of naked planar or quasi-planar small (B_2 to B_6) systems and their potential as new ligands and for material science applications^{144(b)}, chemistry of complexes containing carboranyl moieties including their synthesis, metallocene complex formation and utility of the complexes in α -olefin polymerisation¹⁴⁵, chemistry of adduct of $B(C_6F_5)_3$ with nitrogen-containing compounds like nitriles, amines, imines, N -heterocycles and their use as activators in olefin polymerisation¹⁴⁶, and recent chemistry of transition metal borane, boryl and borylene complexes¹⁴⁷.

Oxidation of $B_9H_{12}^-$ by iodine has been reported as a safe route for large scale production of $B_{18}H_{22}$ ¹⁴⁸. A novel class of *azaboranes* containing glucose or galactose functionalities derived from $\{H_2N(CH_2)_4NH_2\}B_{18}H_{11}NH-(CH_2)_4NH_2$ have been developed for application in *boron neutron capture therapy* (BNCT)¹⁴⁹. Synthesis of the *closo*-thiaborane 1-SB₁₁H₁₁ by reaction between *nido*-B₁₀H₁₄ with S in presence of a base and BH_3 has been reported and from this a series of monohalogenated derivatives 12-X-1-SB₁₁H₁₀ (X = Cl, Br, I) have been made¹⁵⁰. Reaction of the *closo*-carborane anion $CB_7H_8^-$ with a *d*-block metal carbonyl results in a novel insertion of CO into the cluster framework and formation of a series of

C-OH substituted metallocarborane complexes¹⁵¹. The first synthesis of a distanna-*closo*-dodecaborate $\text{Sn}_2\text{B}_{10}\text{H}_{10}^{2-}$ having the two Sn in adjacent positions has been reported that involves intermediate formation of a *conjuncto*-distanna-*closo*-decaborate (2-) having a Sn-Sn bond; the distannadodecaborate (2-) is exceptionally stable and isolated as salt with $\text{Bu}_3(\text{Me})\text{N}^+$ cation¹⁵². Supracarboranes with 13, 14, 15 and 16 vertices have been synthesized¹⁵³. The first structurally authenticated terminal borylene complex with a single B-Fe bond has been reported (IV)¹⁵⁴. Stanna-*closo*-decaborate, $\text{SnB}_{11}\text{H}_{11}^{2-}$ and its chemistry has been reviewed¹⁵⁵, and its complexes with Cd(II), Hg(II)¹⁵⁶ and Ni(II), Pd(II), Pt(II)¹⁵⁷ reported. Boron cluster species B_{16}^{x-} ($x = 1, 2$) have been prepared; the dianionic species has 10 Pi electrons and hence may be regarded as "all boron naphthalene"¹⁵⁹. The analogous germa-*closo*-decaborate and its complexes with Pd and Pt have been reported¹⁵⁸.

Carborane acids $\text{H}(\text{CHB}_{11}\text{X}_{11})$ and the diprotic $\text{H}_2(\text{B}_{12}\text{X}_{12})$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$) have superacid behaviour¹⁶⁰, their salts have been made¹⁶¹ and synthesis of a cationic boron species (V) reported¹⁶². Trimetallaborane systems

$[(\mu\text{-hpp})_2\text{B}_2\text{H}_3]^+$, hpp = 1,3,4,6,7,8-hexahydro-2H-pyrimido-[1,2-a]pyrimidine(1-)

(V)

have been made, viz., $(\text{OC})_3\text{Mn}(\mu\text{-CO})_2\text{Co}(\text{CO})_3$ - $(\mu^3\text{-B})\text{Mn}(\text{CO})_5$ having $\text{Co}-\text{B}$ core and a Au

complex having $\text{Mn}-\text{B}$ core¹⁶³. A review on polyhedral boranes and metallaboranes in medical applications has been published¹⁶⁴.

A short review on main Group complexes containing homonuclear element-element multiple bonding between Group 13 elements developed over the last three decades focusing on their unique structural and bonding motifs

with emphasis on recent discoveries has been published¹⁶⁵. Another review on the application of low-valent Group 13 metal compounds as ligands in coordination of electron-poor main Group as also *d*-block and *f*-block elements also appeared¹⁶⁶. Another review is on lanthanide and actinide complexes having metal-metal interaction with Group 13 elements¹⁶⁷. An interesting Rh(I) complex $\text{Rh}(\text{L})_2(\text{COD})$ ($\text{L} = \text{CH}(\text{PPh}_2\text{BH}_3)_2$) has Rh(I)-C sigma bond and a B-H---Rh(I) *agostic* interaction¹⁶⁸.

A review of the chemistry of complexes of Al(I) with a gamut of ligands has been published¹⁶⁹. Reacting $(\text{Cp}^*)\text{-AlI}_2(\text{OEt}_2)$ with Na-K alloy yields $(\text{Cp}^*\text{AlI})_2$ having Al(II) with Al-Al bond. Further reduction yields $(\text{Cp}^*\text{Al})_4$ which on oxidation by I_2 gives $\{(\text{Cp}^*)\text{AlI}(\mu\text{-I})\}_2$ ¹⁷⁰. $(\text{Cp}^*\text{Al})_4$ on reacting with $\text{U}(\text{CpSiMe}_3)_3$ gives $(\text{CpSiMe}_3)_3\text{U-Al}(\text{Cp}^*)$ with U-Al bond¹⁷¹. The Al(I) compound $\text{HC}\{\text{C}(\text{tBu})\text{N}(\text{Ar})\}_2\text{Al}$ has high thermal stability; it has planar 6-membered AlN_2C_3 ring¹⁷². Reduction of solutions of $(\text{Ar}')\text{AlI}_2$ and $(\text{Ar}'')\text{AlI}_2$ ($\text{Ar}' = \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{-2,6}$ -diisopropylphenyl, $\text{Ar}'' = 2,4,6$ -trimethylphenyl) with excess Na furnished for the first time the "dialuminyne" species $\text{Na}_2[\text{Ar}'\text{Al-AlAr}']$ and $\text{Na}_2[(\text{AlAr}'')_3]$ respectively¹⁷³.

An outstanding achievement in carbon chemistry in the year 2004 was the isolation from graphite a new allotrope of carbon, *graphene*, the structure of which is one-atom thick planar sheets of sp^2 bonded carbon atoms (C-C, 1.42Å) (as in a single graphite layer) and densely packed in a honeycomb crystal lattice. In electrical conductivity it is superior to silver and in thermal conductivity it is superior to any known material and has other properties that make it promising for future applications in many areas¹⁷⁴⁻¹⁷⁷. The 2010 Nobel Prize in Physics has been awarded to its discoverers Andre Geim (UK) and Konstantin Novoselov (Russia).

Important properties of fullerenes have been reviewed^{178(a)}. The effects of carbon nanoparticles on biological environment and the importance of these effects in human and animal health have been discussed^{178(b)} and use of a porphyrin- C_{60} in photodynamic therapy has been reported^{178(c)}.

The very elusive "carbonic acid" has been generated by irradiation with a shot of laser light of a mixture of bicarbonate and a photoacid (whose acidity can be triggered by a pulse of optical energy) and the generated $\text{OC}(\text{OH})_2$ detected by femtosecond IR spectroscopy; its pK_a has been estimated (from measured protonation rate of HCO_3^-) to be intermediate between that of CH_3COOH and HCOOH ^{179(a)}. D_2CO_3 is much more stable in solu-

tion (life time 300 ns; pK_a 3.45 ± 0.15)^{179(b)}. A genetically modified bacteria (*cyanobacterium*) converts CO₂ to isobutyraldehyde, which is of much potential being a precursor to several useful chemicals including isobutanol Me₂CHCH₂OH (a substitute for petrol)^{179(b)}. Carbon dioxide can be used to synthesise isocyanates and carbodiimides using a Ti imide reagent¹⁸⁰; CO₂ inserts twice into Sn–H bond in (Tp)Os{P(OR)₃}₂(SnH₃) to form (Tp)Os{P(OR)₃}₂(SnH(HCOO))₂¹⁸¹ and these reactions are of promise in the fixation of CO₂.

The concentration of CO₂ a ‘greenhouse gas’ in the atmosphere has been increasing steadily since the beginning of the industrialization, from *ca* 280 ppm (v/v) to its present value of *ca.* 380 ppm (v/v) and the trend is likely to continue, despite international conferences on climate changes making proposals for significant reductions in CO₂ emissions in different countries of the world, unless we succeed in finding economically viable alternate sources of energy to meet our evergrowing demand for energy. In this context efficient and cheap methods of scavenging CO₂ from chimney gases of thermal power plants and other industries is a matter of much concern for arresting any further increase in atmospheric CO₂. In this connection it is worth noting that a highly porous zinc-adeninate-pyridine-dimethylcarbamate framework is a relatively cheap, efficient and highly selective absorber and storage material for CO₂ from gas mixtures¹⁸². A magnesium based MOF (Mg–MOF–74) selectively scavenges CO₂ from a 20% CO₂ + 80% CH₄ gas mixture trapping 89 g CO₂/kg of MOF; the trapped CO₂ can be released completely at 80°C¹⁸³.

There has also been some advances in CO₂ fixation to form chemicals of value¹⁸⁴. Two such examples have already been mentioned (*loc. cit.*)^{180,181}. Insertion of CO₂ into a Ru–CH₃ bond in a Ru complex forming the corresponding acetato complex has been reported¹⁸⁵. CO₂ can be transformed very efficiently into HCOOK in presence of KOH and an Ir ‘pincer’ (PNP, see p. 1132) complex as catalyst^{184(b)}. CO₂ is also ‘fixed’ under supercritical conditions forming 1,3-dimethyl-2-imidazolidinone in reaction with *N,N*-dimethylethylenediamine in presence of silicon as catalyst¹⁸⁶. Electrochemical reduction of CO₂ into formate as major product (with some oxalate and CO) using a complex of Fe(III) as electrocatalyst has been reported; the active species is the Fe(I) complex generated in the process¹⁸⁷. Very remarkable is a dinuclear Cu(I) complex (VI) that absorbs CO₂ (2 : 4 molar ratio) to form a tetranuclear Cu(II) complex (VII) having two bridg-

(VI)

● Cu, O = oxygen atom, ⊙ = N, ⊖ = S

(VII)

ing oxalate ions that result from reduction of CO₂ by the Cu(I) species. The oxalate can be recovered in DMF medium by electrolytic reduction of the Cu(II) at a low potential of –0.03 V vs NHE and precipitation of the oxalate as Li₂C₂O₄, reforming the Cu(I) complex which is recycled¹⁸⁸. Other fixation methods have also been reported¹⁸⁹.

A review on catalysis in condensed CO₂ has been published¹⁹⁰. A fullerene-acrylamide copolymer is water soluble and exhibits antitumour activity against bone tumour cells *in vitro*¹⁹¹.

Dark green crystals of an aromatic chair-shaped Si₆ ring compound has been reported¹⁹². A Si(I) compound with a Si–Si bond has been reported¹⁹³, as also complexes having the polysilicide ions Si₆⁶⁻ with alkali metal-crown ether cations¹⁹⁴. Complexes having metal (Fe, Co) encapsulated Ge₁₀ cluster anions [M@Ge₁₀]³⁻ have been made¹⁹⁵, as also the cluster anions (EAl_n)⁻ (E = Si, Ge, Sn; n = 5–8)¹⁹⁶. A review on the antiproliferative and anti-tumour activity of organotin compounds has been published¹⁹⁷.

The uranium complex [{U(η-C₈H₆(1,4-SiPr₃)₂}(η-Cp*)(THF)] reacts with CO forming the squarate-bridged dimer [{U(η-C₈H₆(1,4-SiPr₃)₂(η-Cp*))₂(μ₂,κ²-C₄O₄)] the formation of which involves condensation and reduction of 4CO forming the squarate^{198(a)}.

Ge(II) has been stabilised as [Ge(2,2,2-Crypt)]-[F₃CSO₃]⁻ salt^{198(b)}.

In compounds of nitrogen catenation larger than N₃ are far less common. The species N₄⁴⁻ which is isoelectronic and isostructural with CO₃²⁻ and NO₃⁻ was reported in a dinuclear tungsten complex in the year 1984¹⁹⁹, and unbranched N₄, N₅ and N₆ catenation are known since

long^{200(a)}. Complexes having N_4^{2-} ^{200(b)} and N_2^{2-} ^{200(c)} as ligands have been reported. Other polynitrogen species (other than HN_3 and N_3^-) reported earlier are in 18 binary compounds of N and H (other than NH_3 and N_2H_4), viz., $HN=N-NH_2$ (triazene), $H_2N-NH-NH_2$ (triazane), $H_2N-N=N-NH_2$ (2-tetrazene), $H_2N-NH-NH-NH_2$ (tetrazane), etc., and *cyclo-1,3,5-N₆(NH)₃* (triaziridene). Existence of N_5 ring in pentazoles, RN_5 , is known since the 1950s of the last century, but only in the year 2003 pentazolic acid, HN_5 was made in solution²⁰¹. Marginally stable $(N_5)(AsF_6)$ was reported in the year 1999²⁰² and reasonably stable $(N_5)(SbF_6)$ and also $(N_5)(Sb_2F_{11})$ made subsequently²⁰³ and analogous $(N_5)_2(SnF_6)$ made from $(N_5)(SbF_6)$ by metathesis²⁰⁴. The ion N_5^+ is V-shaped in structure with the two N-N-N arms nearly linear. The $(N_5)^+(N_5)^-$ is also a viable entity²⁰⁵. The N_5^+ is a powerful $1e^-$ oxidizer²⁰³.

Despite being energetically favourable, the reaction of N_2 with H_2 forming NH_3 does not take place unaided by a catalyst. The usual commercial method (Haber-Bosch process) involves catalytic reaction in rather drastic conditions of high temperature and high pressure, but in nature the reaction occurs efficiently under the mild ambient conditions under the influence of the nitrogenase enzymes (Fe-Mo-S, Fe-V-S). A complex formally of $Fe_5^{II}Fe_3^{III}$ having Fe_8S_7 cluster which is actually two cubane-type Fe_4S_4 clusters with a common corner having S has been made which is structurally rather similar to the Fe-Mo-cofactor of nitrogenase²⁰⁶. Some observations of significance are the conversion of nitrogen to ammonia under mild conditions such as the following :

In presence of freshly precipitated FeS as mediator H_2S reduces N_2 to NH_3 ²⁰⁷. A thin film of $Fe_2Ti_2O_7$ photocatalyses the conversion of N_2 (of air) to NH_3 in visible light²⁰⁸. Catalytic reduction of N_2 to NH_3 at room temperature and atmospheric pressure by Mo complexes of tetradentate triamidoxime ligands has been reported, the Mo cycling between the Mo(III) (no lower state as in systems studied earlier) and Mo(VI) states²⁰⁹. Electrochemical reduction of N_2 to NH_3 in molten salts at atmospheric pressure and temperature much lower than in the Haber-Bosch process has been reported²¹⁰. Catalytic reduction of N_2 to NH_3 by *d*-block metal compounds has been reviewed^{211(a)-(c)} and also O_2 activation by low-valent metal complexes^{211(d)}. Perovskite oxides $La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO_3$ and $La_{1-x}Sr_xMnO_3$ are as effective as Pt for catalytic oxidation of NO to NO_2 ²¹². PR_3 species are

versatile ligands usually exhibiting monodentate function. However, in $[Rh_2I_2(\mu-PMe_3)(\mu-CPh_2)]$ the PMe_3 acts as a bridging ligand²¹³.

Some interesting pinctogen species reported in the year 2003 are $Cu_2P_{1.8}As_{1.2}I_2$ ^{214(a)}, $[M(E_8)]^{n-}$ ($M=Cr, Mn$; $E=As, Sb$; $n=2, 3$) as salts of $M^{+214(b)}$, $[Fe(E_5)]^+$ ($E=Sb, Bi$)^{214(c)} and exotic $[As@Ni_{12}@As_{20}]^{3-}$ (isolated as $[P(Bu^t)_4]^+$ salt^{214(a)}); in the last one the anion is an As-centered ecosahedral Ni_{12} that lies in the centre of an As_{20} dodecahedral cage. New synthetic routes for making the ozone analogue of H_2O_2 , viz., H_2O_3 , have been reported²¹⁵.

An important class of aryloxides are the *calixarenes* which have cavities to form complexes with small molecules were reported during the last decade of the previous century. *p*-Sulfonatocalix[4]arene complexes Rb^+ and even more strongly Cs^+ of size matching the size of cavity in the calixarene where the cation is held due to interaction with the aromatic π system²¹⁶. An analogous Calix(6)pyrrole has been reported to have the ability to complex halide ions²¹⁷.

In recent years significant activity has been noticed on the preparation and electronic properties of metal chalcogenides²¹⁸⁻²²³, on molecular chalcogen-nitrogen radicals²²⁴⁻²³⁰ and phosphorus-chalcogen ligands and their complexes with *d*-block metals²³¹⁻²³⁶. Some such ligands are $(EPR_2)_2N^-$ ($E=S, Se, Te$), $(EP^iPr_2)^-$ ($E=S, Se, Te$), $(TeP^iPr_2NP^iPr_2)^-$ and $TeP^iPr_2NP^iPr_2E$ ($E=O, S, Se$).

The geometry of molecules having 7 pairs of valence electrons (6 bonding pairs and a lone pair) cannot be predicted accurately using VESPR theory. Examples of such species are XF_6^- ($X=Cl, Br, I$) and XeF_6 . While ClF_6^- and BrF_6^- display regular octahedral geometry, IF_6^- has a distorted structure. An electron localisation function study of these systems led to conclusion that expansion of the non-bonding electrons from the core into the valence shell occurs, and it is the balance between the energy associated with this expansion and that due to ligand-ligand repulsion that dictates the geometry of these and of AX_6E species with 7 pairs of valence electrons²³⁷. XeF_6 is known to be fluxional and based on detailed structural information at least six different modifications exist as also a dimer formed in presence of HF ²³⁸.

$[Pr(\text{benzo-15-crown-5})_2]I_{21}$ is the first such compound having I_{21}^{3-} and its structure has been reported²³⁹, the previously known largest polyiodide was I_{13}^{3-} .

A review has been published on very weakly coordinating (virtually non-coordinating) ligands many of which are highly fluorinated species. $\text{Ba}(\text{H}_3\text{F}_4)_2$ is interesting and the first such compound reported²⁴¹. Use of UF_6 in the enrichment of ^{235}U for use as a nuclear fuel in nuclear power generation resulted in the accumulation by the year 2009 of 1.7 million tonnes of depleted UF_6 requiring its disposal. Methods for its conversion to U oxides and useful fluoro compounds like COF_2 , MoF_6 , WF_6 , PF_5 , SF_4 , SiF_4 , etc. have been described²⁴². ClOCl has been prepared by laser photolysis of Cl_2 in O_3 followed by its collection in cold trap²⁴³. This has been much studied due to its role in stratospheric ozone depletion over the Antarctica. The triiodate anion I_3O_8^- has been isolated as the Na^+ salt and structure determined²⁴⁴; interest in removal of ClO_2^- from drinking water prompted studies on the use of Fe porphyrins to act as *dismutases* for degradation of ClO_2^- ²⁴⁵. Since the first discovery of a Xe compound, then believed to be $\text{Xe}(\text{PtF}_6)$, by N. Bartlett in the year 1962 there has been considerable steady progress in chemistry of compounds of noble gases, Ng. The first compound of Ar, HArF , was made at -233°C ²⁴⁶. Clathrate hydrate formation by Ne, Ar, Kr, Xe when the Ng is trapped in ice lattice has been reported^{247(a)}, and it is worth noting in this connection the formation of fullerene encapsulated endohedral complexes of Ng, $(\text{Ng}@\text{C}_{60})$ (Ng = He, Ne, Ar, Kr, Xe), on exposure of C_{60} to Ng at high pressure^{247(b)}. Compounds of Kr in +2 oxidation state are known and a review of such compounds appeared in the year 2002²⁴⁸ and another on atypical compounds of noble gases published in the year 2007²⁴⁹. $(\text{KrF})(\text{MF}_6)$ and $(\text{Kr}_2\text{F}_3)(\text{MF}_6)$ which are analogues of known Xe compounds have been made such as $(\text{KrF})(\text{PtF}_6)$ and $(\text{KrF})(\text{AuF}_6)$; the $(\text{KrF})^+$ is the strongest oxidative fluorinating agent known so far and $(\text{KrF})(\text{AuF}_6)$ oxidizes O_2 at ambient temperature forming $(\text{O}_2)(\text{AuF}_6)^{250(a)}$. The unique $[\text{XeF}_5]_3[\text{Ti}_4\text{F}_{19}]$ has been prepared by reacting XeF_2 and TiF_4 in presence of F_2 in anhydrous HF by UV irradiation^{250(b)}. Theoretical characterization of organonoble gas compounds based on general structures XNgCCNgX and XNgCCX (Ng = Ar, Kr; X = F, Cl, Br) suggests that certain species may have enough stability to allow spectroscopic analysis or even experimental synthesis as in the case of FARCCF ²⁵¹ and characterization of organo-Ng dications, such as HCCNg^{2+} ²⁵² (Ng

= Ar, Kr). Synthesis of compounds with Ng–Ng bond is challenging and likely formation of HNg-NgF by strategy similar to that used for making HArF (*loc. cit.*) has been discussed; HXe-XeF is likely to be made in low temperature matrices²⁵³. The first noble gas hydride of composition HNgY (Y = electronegative fragment) was made in 1995 and since then about two dozen members of this family have been reported and future possibilities discussed²⁵⁴. Synthesis of $(\text{F}_4\text{S}=\text{N-Xe-N}=\text{SF}_3)(\text{AsF}_6)$, being the first example of a compound having N–Ng–N bond, has been reported²⁵⁵, and preparation of the first Xe^{II}-oxide-fluoride, $(\text{Xe}_3\text{OF}_3)(\text{EF}_6)$ (E = As, Sb)²⁵⁶, which has a Z-shaped cation $(\text{FXeOXeFXeF})^+$ with linear F–Xe–O, O–Xe–F and F–Xe–F units. Preparation of $(\text{F}_4\text{S}=\text{N-Xe})(\text{AsF}_6)$ from rearrangement of $(\text{F}_3\text{S}=\text{N-Xe-F})(\text{AsF}_6)$ in anhydrous HF and HF– BrF_5 solvents has been reported²⁵⁷. Treatment of F_5SNH_3^+ with XeF_2 in $\text{BrF}_5 + \text{HF}$ provided $[\text{F}_5\text{SN}(\text{H})\text{Xe}](\text{AsF}_6)$; this has the strongest Xe–N bond (2.069 Å) known so far²⁵⁸. The compound HXeOXeH is the smallest known neutral molecule with 2 Ng atoms; it has been made by UV photolysis of $\text{H}_2\text{O-N}_2\text{O-Xe}$ (matrix) at 9 K and subsequent annealing at 40–45 K²⁵⁹. Interesting are compounds having M–Ng bonds²⁶⁰. Thus, reacting AuF_3 in $\text{HF} + \text{SbF}_5$ with Xe under pressure and appropriate conditions square planar $(\text{AuXe}_4)^{2+}$ was made as its salt with $(\text{Sb}_2\text{F}_{11})^-$ ²⁶¹. *Cis*- $(\text{AuXe}_2)(\text{Sb}_2\text{F}_{11})_2$ in which Au has two of its *cis* coordination positions occupied by F^- of two $\text{Sb}_2\text{F}_{11}^-$ anions has been made similarly and is slightly more stable thermally²⁵². Both these are authentic Au(II) compounds. *Trans*- $(\text{AuXe}_2)(\text{SbF}_6)_2$ has been made by reacting finely divided Au powder in $\text{HF} + \text{SbF}_5$ with Xe under pressure and XeF_2 as oxidant. At lower Xe pressure salts of Z-shaped dinuclear $(\text{Xe-Au-F-Au-Xe})^{3+}$ have been made, and finally in less acidic solution ($\text{HF} + \text{SbF}_5$ in 5 : 1 mole ratio) the complex *trans*- $(\text{AuXe}_2\text{F})(\text{SbF}_6)(\text{Sb}_2\text{F}_{11})$ has been synthesised. Crystal structure determination of all these has shown square planar Au with bridging F^- from the anions (see, “Annual Reports on the Progress of Chemistry”, Sect. A, The Royal Society of Chemistry, UK, 2003, **99**, 120–21). Au(I) is known to form²⁶³ $[(\text{F}_3\text{As})\text{AuXe}][\text{SbF}_6]$. The simple species XeAuF ^{264(a)} and KrAuF ^{264(b)} and also KrAgBr ²⁶⁴ have been reported. Species with U–Ng bond have been reported to have been made by matrix isolation, CU(O)Ng (CUO from U atom

+ CO; Ng = Ar, Kr, Xe)^{265(a)} and $[\text{UO}_2(\text{Ng})_x]^+$ (Ng = Ne, Ar, Kr, Xe; increasingly significant U–Ng bond with increase in mass number of Ng and $x = 7$ for Kr, Xe)^{265(b)}. Unstable $\text{XeM}(\text{CO})_5$ compounds have been made by laser photolysis of $\text{M}(\text{CO})_6$ in presence of Xe and similar Kr compounds are also known (M = Cr, W)^{266(a)}. Compounds having Xe–Hg are also known as in $(\text{HgXe})\text{-(SbF}_6\text{)}(\text{Sb}_2\text{F}_{11})$ and $\text{F}_3\text{Si-Xe}^+$ has been detected by mass spectroscopic study^{266(b)}.

Over the last few years a series of metal coordination compounds with noble gas fluorides as ligands to metal ions of the type $[\text{M}^{n+}(\text{L})_x](\text{AF}_6)$ and $[\text{M}^{n+}(\text{L})_y](\text{BF}_4)$ (M = Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, Cd, Pb, Ln; A = P, As, Sb, Bi; L = XeF_2 , XeF_4 , XeF_6 and KrF_2) have been reported and this area has been reviewed a few years ago²⁶⁷. $[\text{Cd}(\text{XeF}_2)_4](\text{AsF}_6)_2$ ²⁶⁸ and the first complexes of Mg with XeF_2 ²⁶⁹, viz., $[\text{Mg}(\text{XeF}_2)_4](\text{AsF}_6)_2$ and $[\text{Mg}(\text{XeF}_2)_2](\text{AsF}_6)$ were reported in the year 2004.

Both $[\text{Ca}(\text{XeF}_2)_{2.5}](\text{AsF}_6)_2$ and also the previously reported $[\text{Mg}(\text{XeF}_2)_4](\text{AsF}_6)_2$ were reported in the year 2007²⁷⁰, and $[\text{Cu}(\text{XeF}_2)_n](\text{SbF}_6)_2$ ($n = 2-4$) were reported in the year 2008^{271(a)} and $[\text{Mg}(\text{XeF}_2)(\text{XeF}_4)](\text{AsF}_6)_2$ in 2009^{271(b)}. There has been significant progress in the field of ¹²⁹Xe NMR-based biosensors for *in vivo* molecular imaging²⁷³. The *teflate* ion is known to form $\text{Xe}(\text{OTeF}_5)_2$ which on reacting with $\text{Sb}(\text{OTeF}_5)_3$ forms $[\text{Xe}_2(\text{OTeF}_5)_3]^+[\text{Sb}(\text{OTeF}_5)_6]^-$ ²⁷².

Titanium compounds including TiO_2 have been the subject of many recent investigations due to their catalytic properties. Asymmetric epoxidation of terminal alkenes by H_2O_2 and Ti compounds as catalysts have been reviewed²⁷⁴, and also use of Ti complexes in enantioselective synthesis²⁷⁵. CdSe assembled into TiO_2 films act as electron source on excitation with visible light²⁷⁶ and composite CdS nanoparticles bound to TiO_2 nanotubes shows enhanced photocatalytic activity on irradiation with visible light²⁷⁷. Titanium dioxide aerosols catalyse reduction of NO_2 to HNO_2 when illuminated with light in the near UV region²⁷⁸. There are reports on Ru complexes that efficiently sensitize TiO_2 in solar cells²⁷⁹. Au–Pd catalysts supported on TiO_2 catalyse direct synthesis of H_2O_2 from $\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$ ²⁸⁰. Codeposited $\text{CeO}_x + \text{Au}$ nanoparticles on a TiO_2 substrate produces active catalysts for water-gas shift reaction and oxidation of CO ²⁸¹. Nitrogen doped anatase (TiO_2) sheets split wa-

ter under visible light irradiation and generate active HO^\bullet radicals²⁸². WO_3 -titanate nanotubes can photochemically destroy harmful contaminants including chemical warfare agents^{283(a)}. TiN nanotubes are useful as cost effective electrodes for dye-sensitized solar cells^{283(b)}.

Photodriven heterogeneous charge transfer with *d*-block metal compounds anchored to TiO_2 surfaces has been reviewed²⁸⁴ as also reactions photocatalysed by TiO_2 loaded with noble metal nanoparticles²⁸⁵. Metallocene catalysts in alkene polymerization²⁸⁶ and similar use of *half-titanocenes*²⁸⁷ have been surveyed. There is continued interests in $\text{Ti}(\text{Cp})_2\text{Cl}_2$ derivatives as potential anti-cancer drugs²⁸⁸ and cytotoxic Ti complexes have been reviewed²⁸⁹. A novel N_2 complex of Ti, $\{(\text{N}_2)_4\text{Ti}\}(\mu\text{-N})_2(\mu, \eta^2, \eta^2\text{-N}_2)\{\text{Ti}(\text{N}_2)_4\}$ has been obtained by matrix isolation in solid N_2 ²⁹⁰.

Oxovanadium complexes catalyse epoxidation of alkenes with O_2 ²⁹¹ some unique chemistry of low-valent Nb compounds with multiply-bonded main group elements has been surveyed²⁹² and studies on side-on bound N_2 complexes of Nb and Ta reported²⁹³. A dinuclear Ta hydride complex reductively couples 6 CO to form a tetranuclear dianionic species containing the non-cyclic $\text{C}_6\text{O}_6^{2-}$ species²⁹⁴.

Reports on structure-reactivity relationship in biochemistry of metallodrugs including antidiabetic vanadium compounds have been published²⁹⁵. Vanadyl compounds that mimic insulin function continues to be explored²⁹⁶⁻³⁰⁰ and spermicidal and cytotoxic properties of vanadium complexes³⁰¹ and antiamebic properties of VO^{2+} and VO_2^+ complexes³⁰²⁻³⁰⁴; those having thiohydrazone ligands are more effective than the common drug metronidazole³⁰². Biological role of vanadium, model V complexes, vanadium compounds in medicine are the subjects of several papers of a special issue of the *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*³⁰⁵⁻³¹², viz., anti-diabetic V compounds³⁰⁶⁻³⁰⁹, anti-tumour V compounds^{310,312,315} and V anti-protozoa agents^{311,312}. Complexes of V have been probed for their insulin-enhancing abilities^{313,314}.

During 2006 several reviews were published on various aspects of metal complexes including those of Cr, Mo and W and their applications, viz., the following³¹⁶⁻³³⁶

- (a) Metal complexes of saccharin³¹⁶.
- (b) Coordination chemistry of vitamin C³¹⁷

(c) Complexes of Cr(III) related to mechanistic comparison of high-fidelity and error-prone DNA polymerases and ligases involved in DNA repair³¹⁸.

(d) Functionalisation of polyoxometallates by carboxylato and azido ligands³¹⁹.

(e) Photochemistry of organometallic and nitrosyl complexes³²⁰.

(f) Supramolecular coordination networks based on octacyanometallates³²¹.

(g) Chemistry and magnetism of cyanido-bridged *d-f* assemblies³²².

(h) Chemistry of carbon-transition metal double and triple bonds³²³.

(i) Application of neutral amides and guanidines in coordination chemistry³²⁴.

(j) Coordination chemistry of stibine ligands³²⁵.

(k) *ortho*-Metallated transition metal complexes derived from tertiary phosphines and arsines as ligands³²⁶.

(l) Photochemistry of inorganic compounds having azide³²⁷.

(m) Homoleptic mononuclear transition metal complexes of 1,2-dioxolenes³²⁸.

(n) Photochemical reactions of Group 6 metal carbonyls with alkenes³²⁹.

(o) Paramagnetic organometallic Cr(II)/Cr(III) redox-active catalysts³³⁰.

(p) Reactions catalysed by water-soluble molybdocenes³³¹.

(q) Chiral salene complexes as homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts³³².

(r) Synthesis and catalytic applications of mononuclear organomolybdenum(VI) dioxo complexes³³³.

(s) Transition metals in organic synthesis^{334,335}.

(t) Migration and cleavage of substituents from donor atoms in coordination compounds of transition metals³³⁶.

Pulmonary immunotoxic potential of Cr(II) complex of 2,6-pyridinedicarboxylate and its synthesis has been reported³³⁷.

Synthesis and characterisation of new heteropolyoxometallates of Mo^{338,339} and of W³⁴⁰ have been reported and fullerene complexes³⁴¹ having Mo and Cr, *fac/mer*-[(η^2 -C₆₀)Mo(CO)₃(η^6 -Ph₂PC₆H₅)₂Cr] and [(η^2 -C₆₀)M(η^6 -

Ph₂PC₆H₅)₂Cr] (M = Pd, Pt). Cytotoxic effect of Mo(Cp)₂Cl₂ has been reported³⁴².

The nitrosyl complex of Cr, [Cr(H₂O)₅NO]SO₄ has been synthesised and its structure determined by X-ray method³⁴³. Photo-induced CN⁻ dissociation from W(CN)₈⁴⁻ in aqueous solution under ambient condition in presence of O₂ forms W(CN)₇(η^2 -O₂)³⁻ of trapezoidal tridecahedral structure (C.N. = 9 for W)³⁴⁴.

Development of Ti-Cr-V and Ti-Cr-V-Mo alloys for high-pressure MH Tank systems suitable for H₂ storage for fuel cell vehicles has been reported³⁴⁵. The Ti-Cr-V-Mo alloy stores 2.4% (w/w) H₂ at 0.1–33 MPa and 25°C. The unprecedented coexistence of cyano-bridged Mn₄^{III}Cr^{III} and Mn₂^{III}Cr^{III} heterometallic complexes in a single crystal has been reported^{346(a)} as also the first structurally characterized Ir polyoxo-metallate K₁₄-[(IrCl₄)KP₂W₂₀O₇₂].23H₂O that catalyses the oxidation of water to O₂^{346(b)}. A trinuclear mixed-valence Mn^{II}-Mn^{III}-Mn^{IV} complex has been prepared which might be structurally relevant to the O₂-evolving PS II^{347(b)}. Other Mn clusters/polynuclear species made are Mn₂^{II}-Mn₂^{III} (347(b)), Mn₄^{II}.Mn₄^{III} (347(c)) and more complex species^{347(d)-(i)}. A polymetallate-based mixed valent Mn aggregate synthesised and structurally characterised by X-ray crystallography is K₁₄Na₁₇[(Mn₁₃^{III}Mn^{II}O₁₂(PO₄)₄(PW₉O₃₄)₄).56H₂O³⁴⁷⁽ⁱ⁾. Homometallic Mn cage and heterometallic Mn_{10-x}Fe_x wheel products have been prepared^{347(k)}. The heterometallic K_{2x}Mn_xSn_{3-x}S₆ (x = 0.5–0.95) have ion-exchange properties^{347(l)}. Three dinuclear Mn complexes have been synthesised that have catalase-like activity^{347(m)}. Photochemical activation of [PW₁₁O₃₉Mn^{III}(N₃)₅]⁵⁻ has led to a novel species, [PW₁₁O₃₉(Mn^VN)]⁵⁻, having Mn(V) nitride unit³⁴⁷⁽ⁿ⁾.

Novel compounds of formula [Re₆E₈Y₆]⁴⁻ (E = S, Se; Y = CN, OH) have been prepared as building blocks for synthesis of new porous frameworks which could be of use in a range of applications such as catalysts, chemical sensors and for gas storage^{347(o)}. Two newly synthesised W complexes (gu)₃[WO₂(O₂)₂] and (gu)[WO(O₂)₂(quin-2-c)] (gu⁺ = guanidinium; quin-2-c = quinoline-2-carboxylate) are reported to have *in vitro* insulin-mimic effect³⁴⁸.

Several important reviews that have been published in 2009 are the following :

(1) Compounds with C-transition metal double and triple bonds³⁴⁹.

(2) Polymetallates of fascinating structures and unique magnetic properties³⁵⁰.

(3) Metal-catalysed olefin polymerisation, a perspective outlook³⁵¹.

(4) Bioinorganic chemistry of tungsten³⁵².

(5) Chromium supplementation in *diabetes mellitus*, clinical studies³⁵³.

(6) Is cyanide a strong field ligand?³⁵⁴

(7) Ecotoxicology of Cr(VI) in fresh water fish, a critical review³⁵⁵.

(8) Physiological functions of mineral micronutrients (Cu, Zn, Mn, Fe, Ni, Mo, B, Cl)³⁵⁶.

(9) Copper chelation in cancer therapy using MoS_4^{2-} , an evolving paradigm³⁵⁷.

(10) Copper lowering therapy using MoS_4^{2-} in medicine³⁵⁸.

(11) Use of the novel composite $\text{Ag}/\text{AgBr}/\text{WO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a photocatalyst for destruction of bacteria in visible light³⁵⁹.

(12) The two Zn_6 sandwiched polymetallates $[\{\text{Zn}(\text{phen})_2\}_2\text{Zn}_6(\text{phen})_2(\text{AsW}_9\text{O}_{13})_2]$ and $\text{K}_{11}\text{H}_2\text{Zn}[\{\text{ZnCl}\}_6(\text{AsW}_9\text{O}_{13})_2]\text{Cl} \cdot 27\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been synthesised and characterised³⁶⁰. There is a report of a new novel type Ni_{12} cluster in $[\text{Ni}_{12}(\text{OH})_9(\text{WO}_4)(\text{W}_7\text{O}_{26}(\text{OH}))(\text{PW}_9\text{O}_{34})_3]^{25-361}$.

Role of iron in catalysis has been reviewed³⁶² as also spin-crossover behaviour of iron compounds³⁶³. Other reviews/articles on iron chemistry published during 2009 are in the following areas :

Function and biogenesis of Fe-S proteins³⁶⁴.

Two new Fe-based superconducting materials are $\text{Fe}_{1.03}\text{Se}_{0.57}\text{Te}_{0.43}$ (T_c increases with pressure reaching maximum value of 23.3 K at around 3 GPa)³⁶⁵ and $\text{LnFeAsO}_{0.9}\text{F}_{0.1}$ (Ln = Tb, Dy, Ho)^{366(a)}; for the latter the T_c depends on distortion of the angle As-Fe-As, maximum T_c 56 K (in case of the Tb compound) when the angle is 110.6° i.e., close to the tetrahedral angle. The analogous La (T_c , 26 K)^{366(b)} and Sm (T_c , 55 K)^{366(c,d)} compounds were also reported. These are of interest being devoid of Cu. *fac*- $[\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3\text{X}_3]^-$ (X = Br, I) have been characterised crystallographically, being the first such complexes to be characterised³⁶⁷. Two-electron reduction of nitroprusside $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{NO})]^{2-}$ produces $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{HNO})]^{3-}$ having Fe(II) which is stable at pH 6, but changes to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{NO})]^{3-}$ having Fe(II) on increasing the pH³⁶⁸.

Several complexes of Fe(IV) have been reported³⁶⁹.

Synthesis of dimeric Co(I) complex with extremely short Co-Co bond has been reported³⁷⁰. A tetraalkyl complex of Ni(IV) has been made and structurally characterised³⁷¹. Three-dimensional coordination networks formed from square-planar Ni(II)-macrocyclic complexes have been applied in selective capture, storage and sensing of CO_2 and also separation of $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2$ mixture resulting from water-gas shift reaction³⁷². Enzyme systems based on Ni complexes have been reported³⁷³. Polynuclear Ni complexes and their magnetic properties have been reviewed³⁷⁴, reviews on various aspects of chemistry of Co, Rh and Ir have appeared³⁷⁵, and recent advances in phosphorescent complexes of Ir reviewed³⁷⁶. The Ru-porphyrin oxidation systems³⁷⁷ and luminiscent Ru-polypyridine complexes with P containing ligands³⁷⁸ constitute the subject matter of two recent reviews.

An entire issue of *Dalton Transactions* of 2009 was devoted to metal anticancer compounds including those of platinum, a few of which are worth noting³⁷⁹. Recent developments in Ru anticancer drugs constitute the contents of a recent publication³⁸⁰. This was published in the journal *Metallomics*, a new journal launched by the RSC (UK) in January, 2009 owing to importance of this emerging area that focuses on the molecular mechanisms of metal-dependent life processes. It is known for quite some decades that at least 25 elements are essential in biological systems of which most are metals³⁸¹. However, excess metals cause toxicity and have to be precisely regulated³⁸². Bioinformatics survey of 1371 different enzymes, for which three-dimensional structures are known, estimated that 47% of them require metals, with 40% of them containing metals at their catalytically active sites³⁸³. In addition to catalysing a variety of reactions, metalloproteins also play a variety of other important roles, e.g., as transport and storage proteins (e.g. metallothionein, ferritin, etc.)³⁸⁴, transcription factors and signal transduction proteins. Metallochaperons protect and facilitate the maturation of metalloenzymes³⁸⁵, control the intracellular concentrations of metals, their import and export³⁸⁶.

Laboratory made $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ like the natural mineral *ferrihydrate* selectively removes As(III) from water. Efficiency is improved by increasing the surface area. The As(III) can be removed by washing with alkali and the material can be reused at least 10 times after a heat treatment^{387(a)}.

In recent years selenoproteins are receiving much attention. While Se is essential in ultratrace concentration, excess of it is extremely toxic. In biological systems Se exists both as inorganic species (Se^{2-} , SeO_3^{2-} , SeO_4^{2-}) and organoselenium compounds from the simplest MeSeH to complex selenoproteins^{387(b)}. A total of about 22 mammalian selenoproteins have been found so far, with almost all containing a single selenocystein residue³⁸⁸.

Platinum complexes such as cisplatin, carboplatin and oxaliplatin have been used for the treatment of various malignancies, especially for testicular and ovarian cancers³⁸⁹. Their anticancer mechanism involves platinating nuclear DNA directly at guanine sites (N7) to generate intra-strand cross-linkings and DNA bending (deformation) and finally leading to programmed cell death³⁹⁰. As cisplatin enters cells either by passive diffusion or via protein mediated transport, e.g., Cu transporter *Ctr1*³⁹¹, which may account for the high systematic toxicity and severe tumour resistance of these platinum drugs³⁹². Hence, smart tumour-specific delivering systems need to be developed³⁹³. To reduce toxicity and increase efficacy of the metallodrug encapsulation of the drug inside macromolecules, such as cucurbit(n)-urils and apoferritin was explored³⁹⁴. Such a strategy protects the drugs from degradation by host nucleophiles, such as glutathione and thiolate-containing protein and increases the specificity of the drugs³⁹⁵. In spite of the importance of the Pt-nucleic acid interactions³⁹⁰, only a very modest fraction of the administered cisplatin reacts with nuclear DNA, and Pt-protein complexes may play an equally important role either as active anticancer species or drug-inactivated products³⁹², which depends on the kinetically controlled equilibrium among distinct binding sites³⁹⁶. Mono-platinized cytochrome c (Cyt c) species has been found to dominate in the ESI-MS spectra when Pt complexes such as cisplatin, transplatin, carboplatin or oxaliplatin are added into the protein solution in a 3 : 1 molar ratio³⁹⁷. X-Ray structure revealed³⁹⁸ that both cisplatin and oxaliplatin coordinate through methionine residues with Cl ligands replaced by S atoms (from two Cys-15) with retention of the 2 NH_3 ligands (in cisplatin). But X-ray crystal structure of cisplatin-bound bovine erythrocyte superoxide dismutase showed Pt bound to N_E of His-19, 2 Cl and one loosely bound H_2O showing that platinization of this enzyme follows an unusual pathway involving replacement of NH_3

and no Cl^- ³⁹⁹. Similar binding of Pt(II) has been observed⁴⁰⁰ with hen egg-white lysozyme. The observed differences suggest that specific protein microenvironment influences whether 2 NH_3 or 2 Cl^- are replaced for the Pt(II) binding⁴⁰¹. Competitive binding of Pt(II) drugs to either N or S donors is a matter of much ongoing debate^{396(b)(c),402}. Studies have revealed several groups of proteins that are related to the Pt drug resistance⁴⁰³

Triple therapies based on Bi compounds are commonly used for the treatment of peptic ulcer, *Helicobacter H pylori* infection and chronic gastritis^{384(a)}. Bi(III) binds strongly to the Fe binding sites of human transferrin and lactoferrin both in the N- and C-lobes together with either CO_3^{2-} or oxalate as a synergistic anion⁴⁰⁴. Bismuth bound lactoferrin $\text{Bi}_2(\text{hLF})$ has been reported to interfere with the uptake of $^{59}\text{Fe}(\text{hLF})$ into rat cells, suggesting that Bi(III)-bound hLF could be recognized by the protein receptor and then taken up into the cells via a *receptor-mediated endocytosis* process^{404(b)}. Since hLF is known to be present in large quantity in the stomach secretions of patients with gastritis, Bi(III) may therefore interfere with iron metabolism or interact with proteins and enzymes in the bacteria. It has been shown that over 70% Bi is associated with transferrin even in presence of 13-fold of albumin⁴⁰⁵. Thus, hLF may play an important role in the pharmacology of bismuth by serving as a major target in blood plasma.

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder with the characteristic presence of amyloid plaques composed primarily of amyloid β -peptide ($\text{A}\beta$, up to 42 amino acid units). $\text{A}\beta$ is normally soluble and present in all biological fluids, and the structural transformation from the native state to a β -sheet aggregation is accompanied by the concurrent gain of neurotoxic function. There is growing evidence of involvement of transition metals (such as Cu) at the elevated level of amyloid deposits in AD-affected brains, and hence detailed information on Cu-binding in $\text{A}\beta$ may be critical to the etiology of AD⁴⁰⁶. EXAFS analysis of $\text{A}\beta(1-40)\text{-Cu}^{2+}$ in a 1 : 1 ratio suggested that Cu(II) is bound to 3 N from three histidines (His-6, His-13 and His-14) and one oxygen of either a H_2O or an amino acid unit⁴⁰⁷.

There has been profuse growth in literature during the last decade in the field of Inorganic Reaction Mechanisms. But lack of space does not permit a broad sum-

mary of the developments. But two significant reports are worth citing. Ultrafast T-jump method has been reported for studies of reactions in aqueous solutions with time resolution of the order of 5 picoseconds and has been applied to a number of different types of chemical reactions including ligand-water exchange reactions⁴⁰⁸. Two studies on kinetics of MoFe₃^{409(a)} and Rh₄^{409(b)} cluster formation reactions have been published. A review on kinetics of Ligand Substitution reactions has been published in the year 2006⁴¹⁰.

Several new Cu-based superconducting materials were reported in the year 2006 two of which are La_{1.85}Sr_{0.15}CuO₄ (T_c, 30 K)^{411(a)} and Sr₂CuO₃ (T_c, 95 K)^{411(b)}. A rare example of a mononuclear stable Ag(II) is Ag(18-ane-S₆)²⁺^{412(a)}. Water-soluble and water-stable Au(II) organometallic complexes have been reported^{412(b)}. [Rh(18-crown-6)(NH₃)₃]Au.NH₃ has the novel 'naked' Au⁻ with N-H...Au⁻ hydrogen bond^{412(c)}.

Monographs dealing with gold chemistry, technology and applications have been published^{413(a),(b)} in the year 2009. Anti-cancer properties of Ag and Au compounds^{413(c)}, medicinal^{413(d)} and biochemical^{413(e)} applications of Au complexes have been reviewed. The silver complexes AgX(PR₃) (X = Cl, Br, I; R = *p*-tolyl) have been tested for their anti-tumour activity^{414(a)}. Cytotoxic activity of water soluble Au(I) complexes have been reported^{414(b)}. Au(I) diphos complexes have been reported to have cytotoxic activity^{414(c)}.

A fairly large number of reviews on various aspects of lanthanide and actinide chemistry including applications of their complexes and their organometallic compounds⁴¹⁵⁻⁴³³, of which two are specifically on uranium^{423,424}. Due to importance of actinide chemistry an entire issue (of 2006) of *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*⁴²⁵ was devoted to actinide chemistry.

During the year 2009 several reviews were published on some aspects of lanthanide and actinide chemistry, viz., the following :

- (1) Organometallic chemistry of lanthanides and actinides⁴³⁴.
- (2) Survey of heavy elements (trans-actinides), their synthesis and naming⁴³⁵.
- (3) Coordination chemistry of uranium⁴³⁶.
- (4) Chemistry of U(V) which is fast developing⁴³⁷.
- (5) Activation of CO and CO₂ by uranium complexes⁴³⁸.

(6) Ability of potentially tridentate 'pincer' ligands (PNP) to form {(PNP)₂U} units sterically analogous to {(Cp*)₂U} and capable of stabilizing a wide range of oxidation states⁴³⁹ (PNP = bis[2-(diisopropylphosphino)-4-methylphenyl]amido).

(7) N-Heterocyclic carbene complexes of *f*-block elements⁴⁴⁰.

(8) Metal-metal bonds in the chemistry of *f*-block elements⁴⁴¹.

A new uranium peroxo species has been made and characterised which is trimeric with the central U having two O₂²⁻ in the novel μ-η² : η¹ coordination, isolated as the salt K₂[Mg(H₂O)₆]₄[(UO₂)₃(O₂)₈].2H₂O⁴⁴². From a solution in conc. HClO₄, Th⁴⁺ has been isolated⁴⁴³ as [Th(H₂O)₈(ClO₄)](ClO₄)₃.H₂O; three new hydrolysed Th(IV) species identified are [Th₂(OH)₂(H₂O)₁₂]⁶⁺, [Th₄(OH)₈(H₂O)₁₆]⁸⁺ and [Th₆O₈(H₂O)_n]⁸⁺⁴⁴³.

In this condensed article I have tried to highlight the developments in Inorganic Chemistry which is illustrative but is far from comprehensive. In selecting the examples I have tried to overcome my personal prejudices as far as possible.

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